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Deep-Seabed mining in the Common Heritage of Humankind

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Table of Contents

Summary	3
1. Introduction	4
1.3 Research question and aim	5
2. Theory/concepts	6
2.1 Concepts	6
2.2 Conceptual framework	8
2.3 Analytical framework	9
2.4 Operationalisation	11
3. Methods	15
3.1 Data collection	15
3.2 Data analysis	16
3.3 Reliability, validity, and replicability	16
3.4 Ethical issues	17
4. Results	17
4.1 ISA structure	17
4.2 Relevant stakeholders	18
4.3 Legitimacy	19
4.5 Accountability	21
4.6 Strengths and weaknesses	23
4.7 Legitimacy and accountability	24
5. Discussions	25
6. Conclusions	26
7. References	28
8. Appendix	31

List of Figures and tables

Figure 1: Concepts visualised	8
Figure 2: Conceptual framework	9
Figure 3: Analytical framework	11
Figure 4: Method steps	16
Figure 5: ISA structure	18
Figure 6: Power and interest map of relevant stakeholders	19
Figure 7: Bar graph summarising sub-criteria results	22
Table 1: Operationalisation	12
Table 2: Summary of ISA strengths and weaknesses	24

Summary

Replacing our fossil fuel dependency with renewable energy requires scarce metals found on the deep-seabed floor in areas beyond national jurisdiction. These can be obtained through deep-seabed mining (henceforth referenced to as DSM). However, significant biodiversity can be found here, which produce ecosystem services that are critical to the health of the oceans. Although there is limited knowledge on the short-term and long-term effects of DSM on biodiversity, initial research has shown it to be detrimental to biodiversity and result in permanent habitat destruction. Therefore, the International Seabed Authority (ISA) is mandated to organize and regulate all forthcoming deep-seabed-related activities whilst ensuring that the marine environment is protected from harmful effects that may arise from it. However, the ISA's legitimacy and accountability should systematically be reviewed to ensure good and effective governance practises over DSM in areas that are common heritage of humankind. This research seeks to investigate this by interviewing 10 relevant stakeholders and asking questions in line with the following sub-criteria: input legitimacy, throughput legitimacy, output legitimacy, information disclosure and addressing concerns. According to the interviewees, the ISA scored medium in most sub-criteria and low in information disclosure. Thus, although improved, it was found that relevant stakeholders do not yet perceive legitimacy and accountability as satisfactory with regards to DSM, which is severe given that the ISA is charged to act on behalf of humankind. Many reasons and accompanying examples were given for the low scores. These included inadequate quality of the website and DeepData database, bias of the Secretariat and secrecy surrounding the procedures of the Legal and Technical Commission. This means that the ISA is under capacitated and in need of reform. Especially considering the differing societal needs and scientific information available regarding biodiversity in the deep-sea since the ISA's set-up in 1982. These findings indicate and explain the ISA's shortcomings which provides optimal opportunities for reform of the ISA. Also, this research fuels current debates in a positive manner, which might make people more aware of this complex yet crucial sustainability issue that will partially determine future energy transitions.

1. Introduction

1.1 Problem description

Climate crisis mitigation requires the decoupling of economic growth from our dependency on fossil fuels, known as the Green Transition (Prandecki, Wrzaszcz, & Zieliński, 2021). It entails switching from a carbon-based economy to a more sustainable one dependent on renewable energy sources (Fouquet & Pearson, 2012). This switch includes the adoption of electric vehicles, batteries, and wind and sun turbines (Davidson, 2019). However, these technologies require scarce metals such as lithium and manganese (Råde & Andersson, 2001). These metals can be found as rich polymetallic nodule deposits on the deep-seabed floor in areas beyond national jurisdiction, henceforth referred to as the Area (Miller, et al., 2021). These areas such as the Clarion-Clipperton Fracture zone (CCZ) in the Pacific Ocean are therefore of growing interest to deep-sea mining investors who can extract the metals (Miller, et al., 2021).

However, the ocean's seabed hosts a large diversity of habitats including abyssal plains, ridges, seamounts, and some of the deepest troughs on the planet (Kennedy, et al., 2019). Most deep-sea ecosystems targeted for mining are extremely sensitive to anthropogenic disturbance due to their ecological characteristics such as being pristine, structured, very diverse and containing a high number of rare species (Niner, et al., 2018). Recovery rates for disturbed sites are also shown to be very delayed (Koschinsky, et al., 2018). Furthermore, the pollution resulting from mining in the Area is difficult to localise and may spread to the marine environment within national jurisdiction (Egede, 2011). Overall, there is limited knowledge on the short-term and long-term effects of deep-seabed mining (henceforth referred to as DSM) on biodiversity and abyssal ecosystem dynamics (Koschinsky, et al., 2018). However, research has shown that nodule removal will result in severe permanent habitat destruction and is detrimental to the sessile species found here (Koschinsky, et al., 2018).

Deep-sea biodiversity provides a wide range of ecosystem services including provisioning services (such as fisheries and pharmaceutical prospecting), regulatory services (such as carbon sequestration), and are culturally important (Niner, et al., 2018). Therefore, deep-sea biodiversity is critical to ocean health and productivity, providing services and intrinsic value from which humans benefit daily (Niner, et al., 2018). Thus, the global dilemma of how to transition to green technology without worsening the ecological crisis remains critical. DSM in the Area is therefore a highly relevant and challenging topic, causing increasing tensions between countries.

The International Seabed Authority (ISA) is an autonomous international organization established under the 1982 United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS), through which countries signed to UNCLOS organize and control all deep-seabed-related

activities (International Seabed Authority , 2023). Thereby, the ISA is mandated to ensure that the marine environment is protected from harmful effects that may arise from DSM (International Seabed Authority , 2023). The ISA is currently developing regulations for DSM in the Area. Especially since areas beyond national jurisdiction are extremely difficult to govern as they are common pool resources and essentially the “Wild West”, requiring clear governance frameworks to manage their conservation.

Furthermore, the ISA is responsible for implementing key governing concepts including the common heritage of humankind, precautionary principle and no harm principle (Lodge, 2012). However, this entails huge responsibility by one organization to ensure good governance in the Area. Therefore, the ISA’s capabilities to practice good governance have been questioned and should systematically be reviewed. As stated in UNCLOS (article 154), it is required that the ISA Assembly must undergo a general review of their practices every five years, which will lead to the improvement of the operation of the regime (United Nations, 1982). Yet this has not occurred, partly because DSM has developed slower than anticipated by UNCLOS (Ardron, 2018).

1.2 Societal and scientific relevance

Legitimacy and accountability are essential prerequisite principles for good and effective governance, as acknowledged by the European Commission (Arnall & Wincott, 2002). Especially in regulating DSM, to prevent environmental degradation and the loss of valuable ecosystem services (Biermann & Gupta, 2011).

Given the necessity of systematic review, previous assessments have identified room for improvement in transparency and legitimacy of the ISA's operations (Ardron, 2018; Wolfrum, 2009). However, the status of accountability and legitimacy as perceived by relevant stakeholders remains unknown. Relevant stakeholders include experts and people who are centrally involved in discussions and with the ISA, such as scientists, NGOs, lawyers etc.

Understanding stakeholders' perceptions is important for identifying concerns, facilitating dialogue, and improving good governance in the ISA's regulations, in line with sustainable resource management principles (Lockwood et al., 2010). The research fills knowledge gaps and addresses the significance of the topic in current DSM debates, as multiple stakeholders interviewed for this research emphasized its relevance. Also, the findings will contribute to making people more aware of possible forthcoming DSM and the complexity of this sustainability issue.

1.3 Research question and aim

The aim of this paper is, therefore, to assess the level of accountability and legitimacy of the ISA as perceived by relevant stakeholders involved, and thus contribute to establishing effective governance regulations surrounding DSM.

This leads to the main research question:

How do relevant stakeholders perceive the legitimacy and accountability of the International Seabed Authority (ISA), with regards to effective governance of deep-seabed mining (DSM)?

The following sub-questions will be used as a guide to answer the main research question:

1. How is the ISA structured and how does it function?
2. Who are the relevant stakeholders associated with the ISA and deep-seabed mining?
3. To what extent do interviewees perceive the ISA as legitimate and accountable and why?

The first sub-question provides a description of the ISA structure and its functions as background information to better understand the organization and place its legalities and to whom it is accountable. This will lead to who the relevant stakeholders are that interact with the ISA and are associated with DSM, for example certain experts. Finally, the third evaluative sub-question directly answers the research question, building up on the research collected by the preceding questions.

2. Theory/concepts

2.1 Concepts

As explained in the introduction, DSM is a complex sustainability issue where many different concepts intersect due to the nature of areas beyond national jurisdiction. The concepts of common heritage of humankind, precautionary principle and no harm principle are central to the discussion surrounding DSM.

2.1.1 The common heritage of humankind principle

The common heritage of humankind principle applies to areas beyond the limits of national jurisdiction and the natural resources found there (Noyes, 2012). Although lacking an exact definition, the principle entails the ownership and benefit of common property must be distributed amongst all people (Egede, 2011). Thus, all economic benefits and natural resources exploited are to be equitably shared amongst all peoples. Common property is defined as resources “belonging to the international community in its entirety” or “shared jointly by all” (Baslar, 1998). Thus, no one owns, yet all people manage the territory and must therefore be represented in any international institution set up for this purpose (Egede, 2011). Furthermore, the territory is to only be used for peaceful purposes and should be open for scientific research, of which the results must be made public (Egede, 2011). The research

should not adversely affect the environment, for it to be held in trust for future generations (Egede, 2011).

The common heritage of humankind principle is therefore stated in article 136 of UNCLOS as a principle governing DSM in the Area for which the ISA is responsible for implementing (Lodge, 2012). This requires the ISA to have high levels of accountability and legitimacy to effectively incorporate it into their good governance practices.

2.1.2 Precautionary principle

The precautionary principle has been proposed as guiding environmental policy in the Rio Declaration on Environment and Development in 1992. Principle 15 of the Rio Declaration (the precautionary principle) states that “where there are threats of serious or irreversible damage, lack of full scientific certainty shall not be used as a reason for postponing cost-effective measures to prevent environmental degradation” (United Nations, 2023). Thus, the precautionary principle protects human health and the environment during uncertain risks (Kriebel, et al., 2001). This can be broken down into four central components. Namely, “taking preventive action in the face of uncertainty; shifting the burden of proof to the proponents of an activity; exploring a wide range of alternatives to possibly harmful actions; and increasing public participation in decision making” (Kriebel, et al., 2001).

As DSM activities are likely to advance faster than the research evaluating the associated risks, adopting the precautionary approach in developing these industries is crucial (Bisson et al., 2023). Therefore, the precautionary principle has an important normative role to play in ensuring regulatory legitimacy and accountability is exercised by the ISA in developing new frameworks to govern DSM in the Area (Fisher, 2001).

2.1.3 No harm principle

The no harm rule in international law commands that states are under obligation not to inflict damage to the environment of other states when conducting or permitting activities in their territories or common areas beyond national jurisdiction (Jervan, 2014).

Regarding DSM, the seabed cannot be exploited without disturbing the superjacent water column or inflicting environmental degradation on neighboring areas (Johnstone, 2015). Therefore, the no harm principle can only be implemented effectively by the ISA in the presence of accountability and legitimacy as states are obliged to assume responsibility for possible harmful effects on the environment resulting from their actions.

Figure 1: Concepts visualised

The principles explained above govern the ISA and should determine the regulatory framework being established for DSM. However, the principles require high levels of legitimacy and accountability within the ISA to be effectively implemented as part of good governance practices for DSM, as they dictate the stakeholders, policies, and procedures operating within the ISA. Their interconnectedness is visualised in Figure 1.

2.2 Conceptual framework

The ISA bears high responsibility in governing the natural resources of the deep-seabed and the growing pressures of countries wanting to mine. Crucially, the ISA must therefore adopt good governance principles to prevent large scale environmental degradation and ensure benefits are equally distributed amongst all peoples.

Focus is laid on the principles of legitimacy and accountability due to their knowledge gap regarding the ISA. Legitimacy and accountability form part of the “five principles of good governance” by the United Nations Development Program (UNDP). Although it is difficult to define a set of good governance principles, there is compelling evidence that these are universally recognized, thus explaining this framework choice (Graham, Plumtre, & Amos, 2003). The five principles include legitimacy and voice, direction, performance, accountability, and fairness. It must be noted that these principles might overlap or conflict according to the social context as their application is complex (Graham, Plumtre, & Amos, 2003).

Legitimacy refers to the acceptance of authority and justification of political power (Mees, Driessen, & Runhaar, 2014). Based on the UNDP text, “all men and women should

have a voice in decision-making” which is built on freedom of association and speech and capacities to participate constructively (Graham, Plumtre, & Amos, 2003). Good governance ensures broad consensus is achieved by mediating conflicting interests. The ISA acts on behalf of all of humankind concerning areas that are common property, thus their authority must be accepted by everyone to effectively govern mining activities in the Area.

Accountability is reflected through transparency, entailing the free flow of information and access to processes to those concerned with them (Graham, Plumtre, & Amos, 2003). Increased transparency in the governance of natural resources (the deep seabed), improves accountability, enforceability, and compliance and therefore leads to more equitable outcomes (Ardron, 2018).

As shown in Figure 2, the ISA is encompassed by the five principles of good governance. Legitimacy and accountability are necessary for the ISA to establish effective policies and frameworks governing DSM to prevent environmental degradation and ensure benefits are equitably distributed.

Figure 2: Conceptual framework

2.3 Analytical framework

The perceived legitimacy of the ISA can be assessed by examining the level of participation and consensus orientation according to relevant stakeholders. This can be obtained by measuring the following sub-criteria. Input legitimacy is the inclusive interest representation and is achieved by equally representing all interests at stake and including stakeholders in the decision-making processes (Mees, Driessen, & Runhaar, 2014). This is necessary to prevent the skewing of interests as the deep seabed is managed by all people, which must be reflected by representing all of society’s interests. Throughput legitimacy relates to the fairness of the process and the procedural justice of obtaining quality rules to reach decisions (Mees,

Driessen, & Runhaar, 2014). This is important for the ISA's legitimacy as it affects the acceptance of authority by all stakeholders, which is needed to introduce regulations in areas that are the common heritage of humankind. Thus, stakeholders' voices should count and influence decision-making. As described by Arnstein (1969), "tokenism", where decision-makers use participatory processes to legitimize predetermined outcomes, must be avoided (Mees, Driessen, & Runhaar, 2014). Therefore, throughput legitimacy is best analyzed by stakeholders' level of influence on decision-making processes and open discussions between them (quality of participation and deliberation) (Mees, Driessen, & Runhaar, 2014). Output legitimacy can be measured by the level of perceived effectiveness among stakeholders and acceptance of the outcomes of the decision-making process. This determines the extent to which the ISA is effective in achieving an effective regulatory framework to govern DSM in the Area.

Accountability can be evaluated using the criteria of transparency and integrity, which are values used as mechanisms to promote good governance (Matsiliza & Zonke, 2017). Relevant indicators were selected according to those used by Ardron et al., (2018), which are shown in Table 1. However, slight adjustments were made due to the scope and relevance of this research. Public participation indicating transparency was left out due to its overlapping with the criteria for legitimacy. Also, quality assurance and information compliance were not included due to the similarity with access to information and reporting, which are more relevant due to the exploratory nature of DSM. Access to information and reporting were also added to the same category due to their similarity for relevant stakeholders included in this research, which would provide more inclusive results in the context of DSM. Access to information/regular reporting entails the regular publishment of environmental information reports made publicly available without proprietary or confidentiality (Ardron et al., 2018). The ability to review and appeal decisions ensures that a mechanism is in place allowing a decision to be revised or reversed should there be reasonable public concern associated with it (Ardron et al., 2018). This can lead to greater public accountability and engagement which is consistent with the principle of the common heritage of humankind (Ardron et al., 2018).

The analytical framework shown in Figure 3 visualizes the links between the concepts, and the way legitimacy and accountability of the ISA are measured, by breaking them up into several criteria, sub-criteria, indicators, and measurements as explained above.

Figure 3: Analytical framework

2.4 Operationalisation

The analytical framework above is summarized in Table 1 below. The indicators were measured using the categories high, medium, and low as defined in Table 1, to obtain a holistic picture of stakeholders' perception of the ISA's legitimacy and accountability.

Table 1: Operationalisation

Concept	Criteria	Sub-criteria	Indicator	Measure: number of stakeholders	Source
Legitimacy	Participation (Of relevant stakeholders in ISA decision-making processes)	Input legitimacy (Inclusion of stakeholders in ISA decision-making processes)	Interest representation (Level to which the ISA acts on behalf of all relevant stakeholders so they are represented in decision-making processes)	<p><i>High:</i> All stakeholders perceive their interests as equally represented during decision-making processes</p> <p><i>Medium:</i> Not all stakeholders perceive their interests as equally represented during decision-making processes</p> <p><i>Low:</i> No stakeholders perceive their interests as equally represented during decision-making processes</p>	Mees et al., 2014
		Throughput legitimacy (Quality of the rules and procedures to reach decisions and the fairness of the process)	Quality of participation (Level of meaningful participation in/influence of relevant stakeholders on ISA decision-making processes)	<p><i>High:</i> All stakeholders perceive having the possibility to provide input to ISA decision-making processes/discussions</p> <p><i>Medium:</i> Not all stakeholders perceive having the possibility to provide input to ISA decision-making processes/discussions</p> <p><i>Low:</i> No stakeholders perceive having the possibility to provide input to ISA decision-making processes/discussions</p>	Graham, Plumptre, & Amos, 2003
			Quality of deliberation	<p><i>High:</i> All stakeholders perceive the discussions and decision-making process</p>	

			(Level of open exchange of argumentation during ISA decision-making processes)	<p>between the ISA and other relevant actors involved as good quality</p> <p><i>Medium:</i> Not all stakeholders perceive the discussions and decision-making process between the ISA and other relevant actors involved as good quality</p> <p><i>Low:</i> No stakeholders perceive the discussions and decision-making process between the ISA and other relevant actors involved as good quality</p>	
	Consensus orientation (ISA's capacity to mediate differing interests to reach a broad consensus based on stakeholders' best interest)	Output legitimacy (Capacity of the ISA to solve the policy issue or achieve its goals)	Stakeholders' acceptance (Perceived effectiveness and acceptance of the governance process and outcomes of the ISA by relevant stakeholders)	<p><i>High:</i> All stakeholders are satisfied with the outcomes of the ISA's decisions</p> <p><i>Medium:</i> Not all stakeholders are satisfied with the outcomes of the ISA's decisions</p> <p><i>Low:</i> No stakeholders are satisfied with the outcomes of the ISA's decisions</p>	
Accountability	Transparency (Free flow of information between the ISA and	Information disclosure (Information by the ISA is accessible, timely and understandable to relevant stakeholders)	Access to information/ regular reporting (Perceived access to good quality information by relevant stakeholders)	<i>High:</i> All stakeholders perceive that ISA reports are made publicly available regularly and accessible to all relevant stakeholders	Ardron et al., 2018

	relevant stakeholders)			<p><i>Medium:</i> Not all stakeholders perceive that ISA reports are made publicly available regularly and accessible to all relevant stakeholders</p> <p><i>Low:</i> No stakeholders perceive that ISA reports are made publicly available regularly and accessible to all relevant stakeholders</p>	Graham, Plumptre, & Amos, 2003
	<p>Integrity (Honesty and trust among relevant stakeholders regarding the ISA as part of good ethical conduct)</p>	<p>Addressing concerns (Concerns by relevant stakeholders regarding the ISA's decisions are taken seriously)</p>	<p>Ability to review/appeal decisions (Level to which mechanisms exist in the ISA that take in concerns raised by relevant stakeholders into consideration and consequently influence the outcome)</p>	<p><i>High:</i> All stakeholders perceive the ISA's decisions to have the possibility to be revised or reversed because of reasonable stakeholder concerns</p> <p><i>Medium:</i> Not all stakeholders perceive the ISA's decisions to have the possibility to be revised or reversed because of reasonable stakeholder concerns</p> <p><i>Low:</i> No stakeholders perceive the ISA's decisions to have the possibility to be revised or reversed because of reasonable stakeholder concerns</p>	

3. Methods

3.1 Data collection

To answer the research question, a combination of document analysis and semi-structured interviews were conducted. Document analysis provided a synthesis of background information such as the ISA structure and relevant stakeholders. Keywords such as “ISA structure” and “ISA stakeholders” were searched in the databases “Scopus”, “World Cat” and “Google Scholar”. This was used to find approximately 36 relevant peer-reviewed journal articles and 4 reports (e.g., scientific reports on DSM effects) no older than 25 years due to the fast-changing nature of the field of study. Furthermore, 3 newspaper articles referred to by multiple interviewees (grey literature) were used and information from the ISA website was retrieved.

This informed the interview questions and determined the interviewees based on their relevance to the ISA. A combination of purposive sampling and the snowball method yielded 10 interviews, conducted through an online Microsoft Teams environment due to feasibility. Purposive sampling was achieved by googling relevant stakeholders within organizations and emailing them. The snowball method was operationalised by asking each interviewee during the interview whether they had relevant contacts for this research. The interviews were conducted in English and took around 30 minutes, within the timeframe of 3 weeks between May 23rd and June 9th, 2023.

In semi-structured interviews, “participants are free to respond to these open-ended questions as they wish, and the researcher may probe these responses” (McIntosh & Morse, 2015). They are a combination of structured and unstructured interviews where the interviewer knows what type of questions they will ask, yet the order and phrasing of the questions are not set, allowing for flexibility (George, 2022). This was most applicable to this research due to its exploratory nature, as semi-structured interviews allow the asking of follow-up questions (George, 2022). Specifically, the research question focused on the perceptions of stakeholders, thus semi-structured interviews provided more detail on their attitudes due to their open-ended nature, producing qualitative data (interview guide found in appendix) (George, 2022). The interview questions were designed to collect measuring data on the sub-criteria (see Table 1). However, output legitimacy questions related to stakeholder’s acceptance of the direction of regulatory decisions on DSM as it has not yet taken place.

Strengths and weaknesses of the ISA and a direct question regarding to what extent interviewees perceive the ISA as legitimate and accountable was also asked. The results were not expressed as a measure of high, medium, or low as they were used to gain a more coherent narrative and build on existing theories. The steps explained above are visually represented in Figure 3.

Figure 4: Method steps

3.2 Data analysis

The stakeholders identified through document analysis were placed in a stakeholder power and interest map. The positions of relevant stakeholders interviewed (and key stakeholders not interviewed) were listed and then placed in the matrix according to definitions used by Newcombe (2003) regarding DSM.

The interviews were each transcribed using the Microsoft Teams transcription function and improved by intelligent transcription in Word (data cleansing). The interview transcripts were manually coded by highlighting the information in different colors according to the sub-criteria in the analytical framework. Thus, important excerpts were read and placed into categories of the sub-criteria where they best fit according to the definitions in Table 1 and then grouped together to write a holistic narrative using the different perspectives. Finally, each sub-criteria were deemed high, medium, or low as defined in Table 1, based on the number of stakeholders (all, not all or none) and their general tone answering questions regarding each sub-criterion. Thematic analysis using a deductive approach gave an overall conclusion whether accountability and legitimacy of the ISA is perceived as high medium or low by relevant stakeholders and why.

3.3 Reliability, validity, and replicability

Results of this research can be considered robust due to the relatively large and representative sample size of 10 interviews with stakeholders from different areas of expertise. Furthermore, triangulation in data collection, where semi-structured interview responses were compared to existing theories and data based on the document analysis conducted increased validity. Especially considering the research question focuses on stakeholders' perception, thus interviewing relevant stakeholders to obtain their perspective was deemed most appropriate. Moreover, the interview guide provided in the appendix and the list of references can be used to replicate the data collection.

3.4 Ethical issues

The interviewees were provided with sufficient research information to make an informed decision on whether to partake in the interview, including signing a consent form based on the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) principles. Personal data obtained from recordings for transcription was safely stored on a password protected computer during the research and destroyed one month after the research was finalized. Also, the interviewees were anonymized according to their preferences indicated in the consent form.

4. Results

4.1 ISA structure

The combination of document analysis and interview data yielded the following information about the basic structure of the ISA. The ISA is made up of 167 Member States and the European Union which are actors within international law, and who are supposed to represent the interests of their societies. Interviewee 2 (lawyer) explained that the ISA is a state-driven process, whereby all states and therefore all people's interests are represented to achieve the common heritage of humankind. This includes present and future generations, developing states, and vulnerable countries.

As explained by Blanchard et al. (2023), the ISA is made up of three parts: the Assembly, the Council, and the Secretariat. The Assembly is formed by all ISA Member States and has the power to establish general policies of the ISA, approve the rules and regulations recommended by the Council and elect the Finance Committee. The Council is composed of the Legal and Technical Commission (henceforth referenced to as the LTC). The LTC reviews plans for activities in the Area, prepares environmental impact assessments, makes recommendations to the Council on the protection of the marine environment, and formulates rules, regulations, and procedures. The Secretariat provides administrative, legal services, and scientific and technical input through its various offices.

The core structure of the ISA is visualized in Figure 5.

Figure 5: ISA structure

As established by the legally binding High Seas Treaty (also known as BBNJ, Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction), settled under UNCLOS, the ISA's mandate includes controlling and administering all mineral-related activities in the Area for the benefit of humankind and conserving and protecting the marine environment. Therefore, the ISA has been developing the Mining Code which consists of rules and regulations for exploring and exploiting minerals (polymetallic nodules, polymetallic sulfides, and cobalt-rich ferromanganese crusts) on the deep seabed, whilst aiming to protect 30% of the oceans by 2030 (United Nations, 2023). Thus far, 31 contractors have been granted exploration contracts (Amon et al., 2022).

4.2 Relevant stakeholders

Many relevant stakeholders are involved with DSM and the ISA, especially considering that the Area belongs to all of humankind. However, the following stakeholders were interviewed: NGO (Greenpeace), DOSI scientist, oceanographer, Ph.D. candidate (youth perspective), lawyers, international alliance, policy officer, IUCN representative and NGO consultant. All relevant stakeholders (including those not interviewed) were placed in a power and influence matrix. Power of stakeholders relates to the influence they have on the formation of DSM regulations (Newcombe, 2003). The interest of stakeholders is defined by their level of involvement with DSM. Figure 5 shows that all stakeholders interviewed, except scientists, have a high interest yet low power in the issue as many have observer status at the ISA, where they can provide input at discussions, yet their opinion holds no legal weight.

Figure 6: Power and interest map of relevant stakeholders

4.3 Legitimacy

4.3.1 Input legitimacy

Three interviewees stated that the interests of different stakeholders are not equally represented, as the ISA is “considering mining interests more than some of the scientific input” (Smith). Four interviewees mentioned the lack of participation mechanisms for civil society, fishing organizations, youth voices and indigenous peoples. Moreover, Evans says that these stakeholders are “basically ignored” and that “growing public pressure” is the only reason their concerns are being adopted and considered by Member States.

Regarding environmental management plans, Robb mentioned that “there's no open call where civil society, scientists or NGOs can make comments on proposals for area-based management tools”. Also, three interviewees mentioned journalists’ lack of access to ISA meetings and two explained the Secretariat’s efforts to shut down NGO and civil society involvement. However, this has significantly improved in ISA meetings since Member States stood up against this. Also, observer NGO’s speaking time is sometimes shortened leading to “informal interaction” between NGO’s and particular Member States.

Singh and Van Der Grient mentioned the opportunity to participate in workshops, webinars, intersectional working groups and commenting on draft regulations, creating inclusivity “to some degree”. However, Robb stated that the ISA selects the scientists who are invited to workshops. The scientists stated that the ISA considers their input, sparking different dialogues, as they do not have an agenda. However, Smith stated that the ISA only

feel obligated to consider scientific studies that they've supported, "not anything in the peer-reviewed literature" which is "not an appropriate perspective on science".

Five stakeholders similarly concluded that "there's a nominal space for participation but not in any significant way" (Evans). Gianni concluded that it is difficult to characterize equalness as all entities involved "have different levels of influence and partly that's structural".

Overall, input legitimacy scored medium by six interviewees, high by three and low by one.

4.3.2 Throughput legitimacy

Live streams of Council sessions can be followed online which increases perceived accessibility and transparency. However, interviewee 6 mentioned that procurement procedures are questionable as individual experts are hired yet how they are chosen is unknown. Also, they are often not diverse, stemming mostly from American academic institutions (such as MIT) instead of prioritizing developing country experts, affecting the ISA's equity.

Although scientists can provide comments on report texts, decision-making procedures and how comments are incorporated in the text is unclear which is "a lack of transparency". Singh stated that observers have "equal footing" to make interventions, yet in practice there is "a hierarchy in terms of observers" as States bring on contractors (stakeholders, not observers) in their delegation during ISA meetings. During workshops, mining contractors are also able to make contributions and suggestions. Furthermore, consistency lacks around the ISA's decision-making procedures, with levels of transparency and public participation often "extremely lacking".

Overall, throughput legitimacy scored medium by seven interviewees, low by three and high by zero.

4.3.4 Output legitimacy

Both lawyers said that ISA decisions regarding the granting of exploration contracts have "generally been fine" due to the limited environmental damage and the high scientific research value in exploration, regarding the costs and benefits of DSM. Smith similarly stated that the ISA has "done a good job in considering scientific input" regarding exploration regulations. Also, the process of developing the mining code and exploitation regulations has been "quite inclusive and quite transparent" due to many rounds of public consultation.

Two interviewees mentioned that current debates at the ISA are useful in shifting States' involvement from passive to active in developing regulations on DSM. Discussions are positively shifting in language as more countries are talking about an ecosystem approach and the precautionary principle. Interviewee 10 stated that countries such as Costa Rica are fighting to get the power back to the political decision, stating that "it's done in a diplomatic human style, but it's quite a big fight". However, one interviewee also stated that discussions are becoming "very polarized" and "quite hostile" due to the lack of compromise.

Five interviewees expressed their dissatisfaction with current directions due to the rushed nature of decision-making and speed at which regulations are being drafted regarding

the lack of scientific knowledge on DSM impacts (violating the precautionary principle). The ISA is under capacitated “over-committed”, leading to “shortcuts”, which could have major impacts on DSM and all of humanity.

Overall, output legitimacy scored medium by six interviewees, low by three and high by one.

4.5 Accountability

4.5.1 Information disclosure

When DSM occurs, contractors are obliged to upload reports of their activities, yet they can block out confidential information, as decided by the Secretariat. Four stakeholders mentioned this insufficient transparency. Singh added that even though ecological data is shared with the public, geological data relating to the resource itself, including the abundance and value etc. is kept confidential which is “problematic” and goes against the common heritage of humankind principle. Several exploration contract violations have occurred as they have not been made public to stakeholders (including Member States). Yet, there is no information on who committed the violations and their nature, thus there has never been any punitive action.

Eight mentioned it is “impossible” to find information (including technical reports and Environmental Impact Assessments) on the “nightmare” website, even if it is available. The site is also not regularly updated, and links do not work, providing an extra barrier to information disclosure. This cumbersome process of looking for and being buried in an overwhelming number of documents, issues, and announcements by the ISA results in Member States’ unequal ability to participate meaningfully in the processes. Stakeholders question whether “is it incompetence or is it purposeful”. Interviewee 10 also explained the conflict where Michael Lodge (Secretary-General of the ISA) says that the exploration for minerals contributes to science, yet the raw data is inaccessible. Evans concluded that the way the ISA governs access to information “fails because if you cannot have timely, adequate and full access to critical information, then there's no form that groups will have meaningful participation”.

Furthermore, a collective database set up by the ISA, where all mining operations data will be added, is useful for data exchange and studying the deep oceans and high seas. However, both scientists labeled the DeepData database as having many quality control shortcomings. This results in difficulties working with it, inconsistent data formats, and possible “replicas or misidentified animals or missing information”.

Finally, four stakeholders mentioned how “the quality of environmental impacts assessments is being discussed behind closed doors in the LTC” leading to a “lack of transparency”. Also, there is “very poor reporting of what happens in the meetings” including interventions and decisions made.

Overall, information disclosure scored low by seven interviewees, medium by one and high by two.

4.5.2 Addressing concerns

Stakeholders with observer status can submit proposals during negotiations, yet the ISA’s consideration of their input depends on internal policies, including their stance on DSM, the issue and its controversiality (stated by various stakeholders). Also, when NGOs question the ISA’s decision making it is seen as “nitpicking or troublemaking”. Interviewee 6 added that there is an “imbalance in how issues are treated”, which is slightly “sinister” as “it’s like somebody’s pulling the strings and manipulating the way the proceedings run” if they are not in line with who is in charge. Furthermore, “there is zero recourse to challenge” Council decisions as there is no complaints or whistleblowing mechanism, reflecting a lack of accountability. An example mentioned was Germany sending an official complaint to the ISA about the Secretary General’s actions being inconsistent with his responsibilities and remit, yet no concrete action has been taken. Furthermore, it is limited who can take an appeal to the International Tribunal for the Law of the Sea (ITLOS), which generates “issues around lack of access to justice”. ITLOS is an intergovernmental organization established by UNCLOS (Article 287) as one of four dispute resolution mechanisms (United Nations, 1982).

Interviewee 7 also mentioned that States have been under pressure and fearful of the Secretary stripping their rights and the extent to which they can legitimately participate in ISA meetings, depending on their stance on the development of the mining code.

Overall, addressing concerns scored medium by eight interviewees, low by two and high by zero.

The interview results stated above are visually shown in Figure 6. Information disclosure is perceived as highly insufficient shown by the lowest overall score, and addressing concerns scored medium, reflecting the ISA’s accountability. The three sub-criteria for legitimacy had an overall score of medium.

Figure 7: Bar graph summarising sub-criteria results

4.6 Strengths and weaknesses

A weakness mentioned by six stakeholders is the ISA's "significant conflicts of interests within the ISA and its mission", as the ISA is both the regulator and (will be) the beneficiary of mining. The UNCLOS mandate on Environmental Protection is therefore "certainly not being pushed forward". Also, three interviewees stated that the institutional framework of the ISA is "very weak and incredibly, profoundly undemocratic" (Gianni). Neutrality issues surrounding Michael Lodge's leadership and his pro-mining stance have been mentioned by seven interviewees. The Secretariat has also provided confidential information to certain parties. Another problem Robb mentioned is the "undue influence or pressure" from a developed country through its metals company on smaller developing countries, such as Nauru (a small Pacific Island developing state) sponsoring a large Canadian Metals Company. DSM is supposed to result in equitable sharing of benefits, yet it is questionable whether the Area serves humankind or mining companies, and the environmental cost involved. The Metals Company would namely receive almost all profits as it maintains almost complete rights and financial control over the project (Lipton, 2022). Moreover, ISA Assembly meetings usually do not contain even half the Member States, which is a legal issue to a quorum and affects inclusivity. Although possibly reflecting a lack of apathy, interviewees stated that this is linked to Member States not having the capacity or financial resources to participate in the meetings located in Jamaica.

Furthermore, seven stakeholders elaborated on the LTC's "fundamental lack of transparency" and bias. Contracts are being issued on behalf of "humankind as a whole, [yet], they're completely secret", leading to a lack of confidence and suspicion. Two interviewees mentioned a scandal (publicly published), where the LTC rushed to approve an exploration permit to the Canadian Metals Company, yet the Environmental Impact Assessment submitted contained many gaps and flaws highlighted by scientists. However, the operation was given a "green light under silent procedure" through an "obscure email procedure" within three days. Gianni added that it is a "skewed decision-making process that is frankly a product of Cold War politics". The last ISA review occurred in 2017, concluding that the LTC should hold more open-door meetings, yet this has not happened despite continuous requests from Member States and observers. However, interviewee 6 stated that committees are technical bodies that make advice to decision makers, thus, "not all of their discussions need to be publicly accessible" as experts need to be able to "express their opinions without feeling inhibited" by autocratic governments. The LTC also has limited "environmental capacity" as it is mostly made up of lawyers and geologists, lacking marine biologists. Interviewee 6 stated, "I think the Secretary general controls the LTC who controls the Council instead of the other way around". Moreover, the New York Times found that some members of the LTC work for mining contractors, confirming interviewees' skepticism about its operations (Lipton, 2022).

However, the LTC is a new regime of people which is an improvement from previous culture issues including "bullying and intimidation". Also, Smith stated that people on the LTC are "looking at all the peer reviewed literature and getting input from a broad array of scientists". Three interviewees similarly concluded that the LTC is "almost set up to fail" as the volunteers (non-experts) nominated by their Member States are overburdened with high

volume and high complexity issues. Thus, the ISA lacks capacity in terms of number of scientists and expertise to develop the mining code in the current targeted time frame.

Regarding strengths, multiple stakeholders agreed that there is participation of every country that is a party to UNCLOS, provoking global participation. It is the first international body that is set up “to regulate exploitative activities in the ocean” which is “groundbreaking and extremely important to recognize”. Also, there is increased inclusivity and awareness about DSM and consideration of who will bear the costs. This positively adds to the discussion on the ISA’s legitimacy and whether it is currently fit for its purpose.

Wilson stated that this change occurred since the two-year rule was triggered. In 2021, Nauru triggered “the two-year rule” (part XI Agreement relating to UNCLOS) entailing that upon request of a party, the ISA shall complete the adoption of rules, regulations, and procedures necessary to facilitate the approval of exploitation plans within two years of the request (Blanchard et al., 2023). This would require the ISA to finalize DSM regulations by July 2023. Yet whether this deadline will be attained remains to be seen.

The summary in Table 2 clearly shows that the weaknesses outweigh the strengths.

Table 2: Summary of ISA strengths and weaknesses

Weaknesses	Strengths
Conflict of interest regarding mandates	Global participation
Weak institutional framework of the ISA.	Increased awareness of who reaps benefits and bears costs of DSM.
LTC: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of transparency and biased operations. - Lack of marine biologists. - overburdened and under capacitated. 	LTC: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improvement from previous bullying culture. - Considering a broad array of peer reviewed science.
Neutrality issues of the ISA’s Secretary-General (Michael Lodge) due to his pro-mining stance.	
ISA Assembly meetings missing more than half the Member States.	

4.7 Legitimacy and accountability

Few interviewees argued that the ISA might be legally legitimate in terms of the treaties established and enforced, yet it is “definitely out of touch with reality in many ways”. The ISA was set up in 1982, where the world had different political, social, and environmental priorities and (lack of) knowledge about deep-sea, the climate regulatory functions and biodiversity existing there. Interviewee 10 stated that “benefits of humankind today mean fighting for climate change and restoring biodiversity”.

Finally, “general issues around accountability and claims of corruption” were flagged. Performance management is non-existent thus there is no “proper structure of accountability” (interviewee 6). Interviewee 7 stated that “it’s very legitimate and accountable for the mining industry” yet less so for the “scientist, the philanthropy and

NGOs". They claim that this is linked to lack of cooperation with other international bodies and lobbying advocacy to not be too involved in the process of large international processes such as the High Seas Treaty. Robb stated that the ISA "has a long way to go in terms of improving its transparency, public participation, and general accountability to all". However, many stakeholders concluded that the accountability of the ISA has "not been properly tested" yet and that this will occur in upcoming years.

5. Discussions

5.1 Interpretation of findings

The findings indicate that the ISA scores medium in most sub-criteria from the analytical framework and very low on information disclosure. Overall, legitimacy and accountability of the ISA is insufficient. Furthermore, although a few strengths were mentioned, many weaknesses were emphasized with accompanying evidence.

First, the website and the DeepData database are both inadequate. This is supported by the findings by Rabone et al. (2023), concluding that the data contains quality issues compromising FAIRness of the data. This includes whether the data is findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) (Rabone et al., 2023). Issues include limitations in the usage of identifiers and issues with taxonomic information. However, the issues identified provide a strong basis for development of the database towards FAIR, which is crucial to adopt in the wider policy landscape in efforts to conserve marine biodiversity (Rabone et al., 2023). This reduces the accountability of the ISA as the transparency of information disclosure which is indicated by the access to information/regular reporting is insufficient.

Furthermore, multiple articles have been published regarding the bias towards a pro-mining stance by the Secretariat and collusion between Michael Lodge and a Canadian Metals Company. A New York Times article (referenced by multiple interviewees), concluded after thorough examination that the ISA provided confidential data identifying the most valuable seabed locations in the Pacific to start its mining efforts (Lipton, 2022). The data was meant to be shared with developing countries to ensure mining benefits are equally distributed and allow them to compete with richer countries (which is part of the ISA's mandate) (Lipton, 2022). This scandal implicates that the legitimacy (specifically throughput and output legitimacy) of the ISA is underperforming as quality of deliberations and stakeholders' acceptance of decision-making processes and the outcomes are inadequate. Also, the ISA's accountability is reduced as the information disclosure process clearly lacks transparency.

5.2 Research limitations

This research had a few limitations that must be mentioned. First, it was difficult to separate interview answers into sub-criteria codes (input legitimacy etc.) as questions and answers oftentimes overlapped. This likely led to research bias in relation to categorizing answers and questions the reliability of the results. Also, it was difficult to know when interviewees were speaking from the perspective of the stakeholder they represent or all stakeholders in general. For example, it was stated that "it's not necessarily that I don't think my organizations

interests aren't represented, but I do think that sometimes the interests of everyone aren't well enough represented". However, the overall tone of perceptions on legitimacy and accountability was clearly identifiable, therefore it did not significantly alter the results.

Moreover, due to the nature of semi-structured interviews, questions were slightly tweaked after the first two interviews based on the responses, which might make it difficult to compare responses. This especially related to the question about "output legitimacy", which provided limited information as no decisions have yet been made on DSM. However, including it did help to understand the underlying argumentation for answers to other questions. Furthermore, purposive sampling as a type of non-probability sampling technique is at high risk for research bias, limiting the generalizability of the findings (Bhandari, 2023). However, speaking to specific experts and people highly involved in current DSM discussions provided a broad range of valuable insights that could likely not have been collected using random sampling.

Finally, certain stakeholders such as fishing organizations and indigenous communities were missing, and interviews were only conducted with stakeholders on the right-hand side of the power and interest map (those holding high interest and high or low power). However, considering the large number of interviews conducted and that different stakeholders generally held similar opinions, the quality of the research remains high. Moreover, this research has pointed out many concrete shortcomings of the ISA according to those who are central to the issue, which may add a lot of value to current discussions and catalyze positive change.

5.3 Implications

This research confirms the ISA's shortcomings in terms of accountability and legitimacy and highlights the severity of this as the ISA are charged to act on behalf of humankind, revealing societal implications. The mandate of protecting the marine environment is currently undermined by the rush for minerals in relation to the lack of science on the consequences of DSM. Moreover, as outlined in the policy brief by Seas At Risk (2023) it should be questioned whether DSM will contribute to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) considering that it will likely generate large amounts of profits for a small set of companies, rather than benefiting all of humankind. Also, it is argued that mining in the deep sea will provide an alternative to mining on land and will be less damaging (Henriques, 2023). However, this has not yet been demonstrated due to the lack of scientific data. Therefore, many call for a moratorium on DSM.

Theoretically, these results imply that stakeholder perspectives play a crucial role in assessing the effectiveness and success of the ISA. Good governance of the common heritage of humankind (the Area) cannot be achieved without high levels of legitimacy and accountability of the ISA as perceived by relevant stakeholders. This was shown through the criticisms voiced and the concluding need for reform of the ISA to handle increasing complexities associated with DSM. Therefore, recommendations for future research include shifting the focus from ISA underperformance, to how this can be addressed, and whether suggested solutions could be effective and sufficient.

6. Conclusions

In conclusion, the ISA is an important organization whose role is key to regulate DSM in a sustainable manner. The following research question was therefore posed: How do relevant stakeholders perceive the legitimacy and accountability of the International Seabed Authority, with regards to deep-seabed mining? Although it has improved, relevant stakeholders do not yet perceive the legitimacy and accountability of the ISA as satisfactory with regards to DSM. Despite holding different levels of standing and positions in the mining debate, many interviewees held similar opinions regarding areas where improvement in the ISA is necessary. However, the ISA is under capacitated and in need of reform considering differing societal needs and scientific information available regarding biodiversity in the deep-sea since its set-up in 1982. Furthermore, reviewing research such as this paper, which identifies numerous shortcomings, actively fuels current debates in a constructive manner and provides optimal opportunities for reforming the ISA while addressing the growing awareness concerning DSM. For example, as mentioned by some interviewees, by establishing a compliance committee, a data committee and a scientific commission or environmental body within the ISA. The ISA needs external, long-standing advisory panels made up of scientists that are not linked to the ISA or ad hoc for a particular task. This may improve the legitimacy and accountability of the ISA and thus lead to effective regulations that fulfil its mandates.

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8. Appendix

Email draft sent to interviewees:

Dear ...

My name is Roos Wiessing and I am a bachelor student Global Sustainability Science at Utrecht University. I received your name and address from Dr. Monica Verbeek, Director of Seas At Risk (my mum).

I am currently writing my thesis on the governance structures of the International Seabed Authority (ISA) with regard to deep-sea mining in the Area. Specifically, I aim to address how other relevant stakeholders perceive the legitimacy and accountability of the ISA in relation to deep-sea mining in the Area.

To help answer my research question, I would highly appreciate it if you would be available for an interview, to gain further insight into this topic on the basis of your expertise. The interview would take around twenty minutes but could be shortened to accommodate your schedule. Your responses will be kept confidential and will be only used for academic purposes. This is further elaborated in the informed consent form attached, which I would ask you to sign before the start of the interview.

Thank you very much for your correspondence, and I look very much forward to hearing from you.

Kind regards,

Roos Wiessing

Interview guide:

1. Could you please describe your organization's involvement with the International Seabed Authority and deep-seabed mining in the Area?
2. In your opinion, what are the strengths and weaknesses of the ISA's current policies and frameworks on deep-seabed mining?
3. **(Input legitimacy)** To what extent do you feel that your organisation has their interests represented by the ISA with regards to deep-seabed mining in the Area? Do you have the possibility to provide input to the ISA? Why or why not?
4. **(Throughput legitimacy)** Do you feel like your organisation has its interests as equally represented in the decision-making process of the ISA when governing deep-seabed mining in the Area? Why or why not?
5. **(Output legitimacy)** Are you satisfied with the outcomes of the ISA's decision with regards to deep-seabed mining in the Area thus far? Why or why not?

6. **(Access to information/regular reporting)** Does your organization have access to all reports composed by the ISA about deep-seabed mining?
7. Do you feel like there is sufficient transparency in the ISA regarding regular reporting and stakeholders' access to information?
8. **(Ability to review/appeal decisions)** When your organization raises concerns to the ISA about certain decision's it has made or are in the process of making, do you feel like the ISA sufficiently takes these into consideration to influence the decision or process?
9. To what extent do you believe the ISA is legitimate and accountable to relevant stakeholders, such as your organization?

Certificate of Consent

I have been invited to participate in research about deep-seabed mining in the Area and the International Seabed Authority. This research is part of a bachelor's thesis of Roos Wiessing for the degree Global Sustainability Science at Utrecht University. The research aims to answer the following research question: How do other relevant stakeholders perceive the legitimacy and accountability of the International Seabed Authority (ISA), with regards to deep-seabed mining in the Area?

My responses in the interview may be recorded and transcribed using teams, accessed only by the researcher, and may be used strictly for academic purposes. After the research is finished, all recordings and transcriptions will be destroyed.

I have read the foregoing information, or it has been read to me. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions I have asked and have been answered to my satisfaction. I consent voluntarily to be a participant in this study.

Print Name of Participant _____

Signature of Participant _____

Date _____

Day/month/year

Optional:

I want to remain anonymous in the research.

Interview stakeholders completed (chronological order)

- Interviewee 1: Joám Evans- Consultant for NGOs.
- Interviewee 2: Samantha Robb- Lawyer working with NIOZ and NILOS.
- Interviewee 3: Jesse Van Der Grient- Deep Ocean Stewardship Initiative (DOSI), co-lead for the Minerals working group, scientist.
- Interviewee 4: Matthew Gianni- Co-founder of Deep-Sea Conservation Coalition (international alliance), observer status at ISA.
- Interviewee 5: Pradeep Singh- IUCN representative (intergovernmental organization and observer to the ISA). He is a fellow at Research Institute for Sustainability in Potsdam, accredited observer to the ISA and member of two IUCN commissions: World Commission on Environmental Law & Commission for Ecosystem Management (IUCN delegation representative in ISA meetings).
- Interviewee 6: Freelance lawyer and legal advisor to different types of stakeholders (including governments, NGOs, intergovernmental agencies etc.).
- Interviewee 7: Worked at an NGO on deep seabed mining issues and now a PhD candidate on ocean governance.
- Interviewee 8: Craig Smith- Oceanographer, studying biodiversity and potential mining impacts and conservation measures in the Clarion-Clipperton zone area since the early 90s. Has also worked with the ISA directly, NGOs and contractors, advising and helping to form exploration guidelines.
- Interviewee 9: Emma Wilson- Policy officer for the Deep-Sea Conservation Coalition.
- Interviewee 10: Ocean companion for Greenpeace.